

Drift capacity models for modern URM walls

Background document for the masonry chapter in EC8 Part 1

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Changes: 1) Further analyses to the influence of the number of rows on the drift capacity are added; 2) A third drift capacity model, which is a function of the failure mode, the axial load ratio and the unit type is added.

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1 Objectives of this document

This document presents proposals for the drift capacities of modern unreinforced masonry (URM) walls. The motivation and objectives of this proposal are as follows:

- The current version of Eurocode 8 Part 1 [1] does not contain drift limits for URM walls. The data basis for the drift limits contained in the current version of Eurocode 8 Part 3 [2] is not clear.
- A large variety of modern URM typologies exists. It is at present not clear to which extent they lead to different drift capacities. The objective of this document is to investigate the influence of key parameters (unit typology, void ratio of units, bed joints, head joints and mortar types) and to evaluate
 - Whether the available data set is sufficient to justify a specific drift capacity model. If this is the case,
 - Whether the influence of the parameter is significant.
- By sharing all Matlab-files that are used to post-process and analyse the data set as well as produce the figures, the applied methods can be easily reviewed. By making the derivation of the drift capacities traceable and reproducible, it should foster the consensus building process on drift capacity models used in design calculations and allow for a faster improvement of the models in the future.
- The analysis is based on the European masonry database collected by ZAG, University of Pavia and EPFL [3].
- Sharing the files should also facilitate the updating of the report in the future, when new tests have been added to the database.

The files can be downloaded from Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) using the following DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2536830

2 Abbreviations and Terminology

Unit types:

HC	Hollow clay units
SB	Solid bricks units
LHC	Lightweight hollow clay units
CS	Calcium-silicate units
LC	Light-weight concrete units
CB	Concrete blocks
HCB	Hollow concrete blocks
AAC	Autoclaved aerated concrete units
LAC	Light-weight aggregate concrete units

Mortar types:

GP	General purpose mortar
TL	Thin layer mortar
LM	Lightweight mortar

Other abbreviations:

ALR	Axial load ratio = axial stress / masonry compressive strength
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Terminology:

Drift capacity	The drift capacity refers here to the drift at 20% drop of the force capacity, or, when this was not attained in the test, to the maximum drift obtained experimentally. The drift attained in the positive and negative direction is taken as drift capacity of the test unit.
Normalised drift capacity	The drift capacity is normalised by the shear span to wall height ratio and/or the aspect ratio

3 Data set used for drift capacity models

The data set used for deriving the drift capacity models is based on a pre-publication version of the European masonry database [3]; the last entry / modification of the accessed version dates from 20.4.2018. The data base contained at this date 497 test units.

3.1 Definition of the drift capacity

3.1.1 Definition of δ_u^+ and δ_u^-

The database lists values of δ_u^+ and δ_u^- , which are the drifts that correspond to a 20% drop in strength. These drift values were defined from the horizontal force-displacement envelopes. However, the three institutions that contributed to the database used two different definitions for δ_u^+ and δ_u^- . For this reason, the three values are preserved in the database. The following definitions were applied:

Pavia: The first comprehensive work on ultimate drift capacities of URM walls is the work by Frumento et al. [4]. In this work, force-displacement envelopes were defined for the first, second and third cycles of each drift level for the positive and the negative loading direction. For each of these envelopes, the ultimate drift capacity was defined as the drift at 20% drop in strength. The ultimate drift capacity was then defined as the minimum value of these six drift values (Eq. 3.4 in [4]):

$$\delta_u = \min(\delta_{u,1}^+, \delta_{u,1}^-, \delta_{u,2}^+, \delta_{u,2}^-, \delta_{u,3}^+, \delta_{u,3}^-) \quad (1)$$

The same definition was adopted in the recent work on modern masonry by Morandi et al. [5]. The positive and negative values given in the database are therefore defined as follows:

$$\delta_u^+ = \min(\delta_{u,1}^+, \delta_{u,2}^+, \delta_{u,3}^+) \quad (2)$$

$$\delta_u^- = \min(\delta_{u,1}^-, \delta_{u,2}^-, \delta_{u,3}^-) \quad (3)$$

ZAG and EPFL: ZAG and EPFL considered only the envelopes of the entire force-displacement hysteresis, i.e., treating all cycles together. Therefore, δ_u^+ and δ_u^- are the drift values that correspond to a 20% drop in strength of this one envelope for the positive and the negative loading direction. EPFL entries relate mainly to stone masonry walls; for this reason, in the following, the drift values defined by Pavia will be compared to those defined by ZAG.

Figure 1a shows the drift capacity defined by ZAG vs the drift capacity defined by Pavia. It shows that the two definitions lead to 10% difference with the ZAG definition leading to higher values. In the following, the drift definition by ZAG will be used. For a discussion of this choice and the association of δ_u with a limit state, see Section 10.4.

3.1.2 Definition of δ_u

In previous works on the drift capacity of URM walls the minimum value of the ultimate drift in the positive and negative loading direction was taken as drift capacity:

$$\delta_u = \min(\delta_u^+, \delta_u^-) \quad (4)$$

This approach was established by Frumento et al. [4] and has also been used in subsequent works [5], [6].

It is argued here that, in order to remove unnecessary conservatism, the maximum of the two values should be taken as this corresponds to the definition of the displacement demand. The displacement demand is related to the spectral displacement, which is the maximum absolute displacement. In the following, the ultimate drift capacity will therefore be defined as:

$$\delta_u = \max(\delta_u^+, \delta_u^-) \quad (5)$$

Using Equation (5) instead of (4) leads to drift capacities that are in average 10% higher.

Figure 1: Drift capacity δ_u defined by Pavia and ZAG (a). Ratio of maximum to minimum value of drift capacity in the positive and negative direction (b).

3.2 Data consolidation

The European masonry database comprises entries from three research teams. In the spirit of documenting all entries, all of the data was entered into the database and in particular for modern masonry for several test units entries from ZAG and Pavia exist. For the purpose of developing empirical drift capacity models, it is necessary to consolidate the database. To do so, the following rules were applied:

Drift capacity:

- If only the ultimate displacement and not the ultimate drift was defined, the ultimate drift was computed as $\delta_u = \Delta_u / h_{drift}$ where h_{drift} is the height of the LVDT measuring the horizontal displacement. If this entry was not defined, h_{drift} was set equal to the wall height h_{wall} .
- If the ultimate drift was defined by ZAG and Pavia, the ultimate drift in the positive and the negative direction were taken as the ultimate drift values δ_u^+ and δ_u^- defined by ZAG.

Axial load ratio (ALR):

- If the experimental compressive strength f_{exp} was available, the ALR was computed as σ_0 / f_{exp} .
- If f_{exp} was not available but the estimated compressive strength according to EC6 was given (f_{EC6}), the axial load ratio was computed as σ_0 / f_{EC6} .
- If neither was available, the test was not considered (see next section).

Failure mode:

- The failure mode was taken according to the information by Pavia (Failure type classes starting with S or D where classified as shear failure, with H as hybrid failure and with F as flexural failure). If the failure mode was not defined by Pavia, the failure mode defined by ZAG was considered (same rules as for Pavia). If this information was also not available, the failure mode listed under “personal opinion” was considered (same rules as for Pavia; failure modes ROB or OVT were also classified as flexural failure).

3.3 Selection criteria for data set for drift capacity models

For the derivation of the drift capacity models only the entries of the European masonry database that fulfil certain selection criteria were retained. These are outlined in the following. Note that the selection was made with the intention of deriving drift capacity models and not strength capacity models. Entries were retained if they fulfilled all of the following criteria:

- Axial load ratio (ALR) is available.
- The test unit passes the quality check. The same quality check as in [7] is applied. It checks whether the maximum force is less than 1.1 times the theoretical rocking capacity:

$$V_{max} \leq 1.1 \cdot V_{rock} \text{ with } V_{rock} = N \cdot \frac{l_{wall}}{2 \cdot h_0}$$

where N is the axial load applied to the wall and h_0 is the height of zero moment above the base, which was computed from the height of the wall h and the ratio h_0/h . The test unit could therefore only pass the quality check if both h_0/h and the axial load were available, i.e., only if the static and kinematic boundary conditions were known. This criterion was introduced as it is known that these boundary conditions influence the drift capacity [8]. Many walls that were tested as cantilevers applied the horizontal load at mid-height of the loading beam on top of the wall but the height recorded in the test report or paper might correspond to the height of the wall only. This introduces an error. To allow for a small error that might result from such test setups, the ratio between maximum force and theoretical rocking capacity was set to 1.1.

- The test was a cyclic test. This selection criterion was applied because it is known that the load history influences the drift capacity of URM walls [9]. In particular, it is known that monotonic tests tend to lead to larger drift capacities than cyclic tests.
- An ultimate drift value (δ_u) is available.
- The test unit represents unreinforced masonry; test units with reinforcement or strengthened or retrofitted test units are not considered.
- Stone masonry test units as well as units constructed with tuff blocks are not considered. Drift capacity models for these walls are derived in [7].

Figure 2 shows that for five out of the eight modern masonry categories more than ten tests are available after applying the selection criteria. These are: HC (115), SB (53), AAC (25), CS (18), LAC (11). For LC (2) and CB (1) only very few and for LHC and HCB zero test units were available after applying the selection criteria. These are in total 225 test units. Note that the failure mode is not yet a selection criterion. The necessity of introducing a minimum height limit and minimum number of rows is discussed in the following section.

Figure 2: Number of test units available and retained for the various masonry typologies. Note that the scale of the y-axes of the two figures is different.

3.4 File register

read_Excel_file_and_data_consolidation.m	Reads database as Excel file, renames columns according to the variable names defined in Database_Z_P_L_new_column_names.xlsm in order to obtain variable names that are Matlab compatible, does data consolidation for the variables used in drift capacity analysis and writes mat-file.
fig_number_of_tests_that_remain.m	Figure 2
standard_figure_settings.m	File that is used for setting plotting parameters for all figure plots
define_and_save_flag.m	File that analyses which test units pass the selection criteria defined in this section and saves the mat-file with the remaining test units. Mat-file before applying a minimum height requirement: DatabaseZPL_for_drift_model_of_modern_masonry.mat (+corresponding txt-file) Mat-file after applying a minimum height requirement of 1.6 m (see next section): DatabaseZPL_for_drift_model_of_modern_masonry_min_height.mat (+corresponding txt-file)
fig_ZAG_Pavia_1.m	Figure 1a and b

4 Influence of the test unit size on the drift capacity

Previous studies have shown that the drift capacity decreases with increasing test unit size [8], [10]. Because real walls tend to be larger than wall units tested in the laboratory, the test unit size is a critical parameter when deriving empirical drift capacity models. Considering, however, only storey-high test units when deriving the drift capacity model would limit the data set significantly. While in [8] a drift capacity model was proposed that accounted for the size of the wall, more recent studies introduced minimum size limits when developing empirical drift capacity relationships, i.e., in [11] and [5] only walls with a wall height ≥ 1.5 m are considered.

In [11] also a limit on the wall length is introduced (> 1 m), while in [5] the height limit is complemented by a limit on the row number (≥ 8 rows). In the following, it is investigated whether the current data set also suggests that the size of the test unit influences the drift capacity and from which size onwards the size effect on the drift capacity might diminish.

Figure 3 shows the drift capacity as a function of the ALR. Furthermore, the wall height in metres and in number of rows respectively is distinguished. The solid lines show the moving average for bins of axial load ratios (bin width: 0.05). It shows that walls with a height of less than 1.25 m or less than 8 rows lead to larger drift capacities. It seems as if walls with 15-19 rows lead to the largest drifts, which is due to the overrepresentation of solid brick masonry walls in this particular bin. Solid clay brick masonry walls tend to have the largest number of brick rows as the brick height is much smaller than for other masonry typologies.

If the wall height in metres is taken as an indicator for the wall size, then walls with a height of $h_{\text{wall}} \geq 2.5$ m can be taken as storey high walls, i.e., as test units that were tested at full-scale. The data suggests that walls with h_{wall} smaller than 1.25 m lead to drift capacities that are significantly larger than storey high walls. Walls with $h_{\text{wall}} = 1.25$ -2.0 m to drift capacities that are for some height bins approximately 50% higher than the drift capacity of walls with $h_{\text{wall}} > 2.0$ m. Two factors might influence these trends: First, smaller walls might be tested more frequently as cantilever walls as therefore lead to larger drift capacities. Second, the units might not be represented equally in all height bins. These two points are investigated further in the following.

Figure 3: Effect of the wall height on the drift capacity: Height in metres (a) and height as number of rows (b).

Do small walls lead to larger drift capacities because they were more frequently tested as cantilevers?

It is known that walls tested as cantilevers lead to larger drift capacities than walls subjected to double-bending [8]. One hypothesis is therefore that smaller walls were more frequently tested as cantilevers and therefore lead to larger drift capacities. Previous works have shown that the height of zero moment has an almost linear effect on the drift capacity [8], [10]–[13]. Normalising the drift capacity therefore by h_{wall}/h_0 reduces the influence of the shear span. Figure 4a shows that the normalisation of the drift capacity reduces in fact the difference between the various height bins. However, the walls with a height of less than 1.25 m still lead to considerable larger drift capacities. For all other height bins, however, the differences nearly vanish and the same applies for the number of rows with the exception of the bin with 15-19

rows (Figure 4b). The latter might be due because walls with many rows were most often walls constructed with solid bricks. This is investigated in the next paragraph.

Figure 4: Effect of the wall height on the *normalised* drift capacity: Height in metres (a) and height as number of rows (b).

Do small walls lead to larger drift capacities because they were more frequently built with units that lead to larger drift capacities?

In order to investigate this hypothesis, the trends for a single masonry typology are plotted in Figure 5, which shows the influence of the wall size for HC masonry walls only. The data for hybrid and flexural failure modes shows clear that walls with heights lower than 1.25 m lead to larger drift capacities than taller walls (Figure 5a). These should therefore definitely be excluded. The limit should therefore lie between 1.25-1.50 m. For this reason, it is decided to comply with the previous studies [5], [11] and exclude walls with $h < 1.5$ m. Figure 5b shows that walls with less than 8 rows also lead to larger drift capacities. Figure 5c shows the influence of the number of brick rows on the drift capacity. It further confirms that lower number of brick rows seem to lead to larger drift capacities. To exclude that this results only from the certainly strong positive correlation between number of brick rows and wall height, Figure 5c is replotted considering walls that have similar heights (Figure 7). These plots confirm the influence of the number of brick rows. They further show that the drift capacities obtained with 7 or less brick rows are considerably higher than for 8 or more brick rows. This limit of a minimum number of 8 brick rows is therefore, as suggested in [5], also applied. Note, however, that applying a normalisation term for the wall height h_{wall}/h_{ref} as suggested in [8] seems to remove the need for applying a limit on the brick rows (here h_{ref} was set to 2.4 m). Because such a size dependent term has only been put forward by one research group, questions with regard to the form of the size dependent term remain (see [8]) and can therefore not yet be considered as accepted within the research community, it is not pursued further.

For the following investigations, it is decided to omit walls with $h_{wall} < 1.5$ m and/or less than 8 rows. If walls with $h_{wall} \geq 1.5$ m and more than 8 rows are considered, 135 out of the 225 walls remain. 31 test units are disregarded because they do not meet the height limit, 44 because they do not pass the row limit and 15 do not pass either limit.

Figure 5: HC masonry walls only: Effect of the wall height on the *normalised* drift capacity: Height in metres (a) and height as number of rows (b and c; c with a finer discretisation). Plot d shows the same data as c but this time the normalisation includes also the size dependent term according to [8].

Figure 6: HC masonry walls only: Effect of the number of brick rows on the *normalised* drift capacity of walls *within a certain height range*: Height in metres (a) and height as number of rows (b and c; c with a finer discretisation).

Figure 7: Number of wall tests for various height bins. The walls that do not pass the height and/or row limit are not considered in the following chapters.

The 135 tests that remain comprise the following tests:

- HC: 57
- SB: 23
- CS: 18
- CB: 1
- AAC: 25
- LAC: 11

For all unit typologies apart from LAC, walls with an aspect ratio $h_{wall}/l_{wall} > 1.5$ constitute less 50% of the test units (Figure 8). The large majority of the walls was tested in double-bending (Figure 9). Most other walls were tested as cantilevers. Other boundary conditions are only available for walls with HC units, where 3 walls were tested with $h_0/h_{wall}=0.75$ and 1.5 respectively [14].

Figure 8: Dataset after applying the height limit of 1.5 m: Slenderness ratio of walls as a function of the unit type.

Figure 9: Dataset after applying the height limit of 1.5 m: Slenderness ratio of walls as a function of the unit type.

4.1 File register

fig_size_effect_1.m	Figure 3 b
fig_size_effect_2.m	Figure 3 a
fig_size_effect_4.m	Figure 4 a
fig_size_effect_4b.m	Figure 4 b
fig_size_effect_4_HC.m	Figure 5 b (updated in 2022 because moving average line was incorrect)
fig_size_effect_4b_HC.m	Figure 5 a (updated in 2022 because moving average line was incorrect)
fig_size_effect_4b_HC_finer.m	Figure 5 c
fig_size_effect_4b_HC_finer_height_normalised.m	Figure 5 d
fig_size_effect_4b_HC_2022_with_height_limit.m	Figure 7a-c
fig_size_effect_3.m	Figure 7
fig_distr_H_div_L_1.m	Figure 8 a
fig_distr_H_div_L_2.m	Figure 8 b
fig_distr_H0_div_H_1.m	Figure 9 a
fig_distr_H0_div_H_1.m	Figure 9 b

5 Influence of the ALR, the shear span and the failure mode on the drift capacity

Most current models in codes use the failure mode as key criterion or even only criterion when assigning the expected drift capacity. An overview on criteria considered by various empirical drift capacity models is given in Table 1 of [11], which is reproduced below. Figure 10 shows the drift capacity and normalised drift capacities using different factors for the normalisation as a function of the failure mode for all walls. Figure 11 shows the same information, this time for HC walls only. Figure 12 shows the non-normalised drift capacities using separate plots for the five unit types for which more than 10 tests are available.

Table 1: Models to estimate drift capacity of URM walls with considered parameters [11]

Model	Failure mode	Wall geometry	Brick geometry	Moment distr.	Axial load	Material param.	Mech. deriv.
EC8 [2]	x	x		x			
NTC [15]	x						
ASCE 41 [16]	x	x					
NZSEE [17]	x	x					
SIA D 0237 [18]				x	x	x	
Petry & Beyer [8]		x		x	x	x	
Salmanpour et al. [19]				x	x	x	
Priestley et al. [20]	x	x				x	x ¹
Wilding & Beyer [21]	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

1) constant value of drift capacity for flexure controlled walls derived, drift capacity for shear controlled ones is empirical estimate

Should the drift capacity be a function of the ALR?

The ALR has a strong influence on the drift capacity c , [11], [19], [22]–[25], most notably for walls failing in a hybrid or flexural mode. For walls failing in shear, the influence is not visible in Figure 10-Figure 12. The figures even suggest a positive trend, which—based on our mechanical understanding of factors influencing the drift capacity—must, however, be a spurious effect. In [11], the influence of the ALR is analysed in detail by studying individual test series and also trends predicted by mechanical models. This led to the following findings:

- In most test series, the drift capacity of walls failing in shear reduces with ALR, in some it does not. It is not clear in which regard the two groups of test series differ. Note that for stone masonry walls ALR influences the drift capacity of walls failing in shear (Figure 17 in [6]). A key difference between most modern masonry walls and stone masonry walls is the behaviour of the units. For modern brick masonry walls crushing of the units is typically part of the failure mode while this is not the case for stone masonry walls.
- The mechanical model for the drift capacity of walls failing in shear with units that are prone to crushing shows that there is an influence of the ALR on the drift capacity (Figure 13 and 14 in [11]). This is also confirmed by numerical studies (Figure 16 in [26]). This influence is stronger for walls failing in a hybrid or flexural mode than for walls failing in shear.

Based on these findings, the drift capacity of modern masonry walls should be a function of the ALR for walls failing in flexure or a hybrid mode. This is supported by the data in the database (Figure 10-Figure 12), our mechanical understanding of the drift capacity and numerical simulations. For walls failing in shear, the reduction in drift capacity with increasing ALR is less strong. Nevertheless, a fair number of test series show that this trend exists also for walls failing in shear [8], [11], [19], [22]–[25]. If the entire data set is analysed, however, the influence of the ALR on the drift capacity of walls failing in shear is not evident. Such a trend for walls failing in shear is, however, evident for CS and AAC walls.

For the drift capacity models it is suggested to take the following approach:

- Make drift capacity model for walls failing in shear independent of the ALR.
- Make drift capacity model for walls failing in a hybrid or flexural mode dependent on the ALR.
- Limit for both failure modes the axial load ratio to 0.3 because there is very little information on walls subjected to higher ALRs.

Note that the ALR of a wall typically varies during an earthquake. One source can be the vertical accelerations of the ground motion. Another further important source is the variation of ALR due to the coupling effect by spandrels and slabs. The variation in ALR from the coupling effect can be substantial and is synchronised with the drift demand, i.e., the larger change in ALR occurs typically for the largest drift demand. Numerical studies [27] have shown that the ALR at the point when the drift capacity is reached should be considered, i.e., the drift capacity of a wall cannot be calculated a priori to a pushover analysis when the ALR to gravity loads only are known.

Should normalised or non-normalised drift capacities be used?

The non-normalised drift is simply the horizontal displacement divided by the wall height. The term normalised drift refers here to the drift multiplied by a term to account for the shear span or aspect ratio of the wall. The objective of the normalisation is to reduce the scatter and to reduce differences between drift capacities of the various failure modes in order to specify only a single drift capacity model. The scatter is here quantified by the coefficient of variation of the drift capacities obtained for a specific failure mode. The focus lies in particular on the scatter of the drift capacities failing in shear because i) these walls rather than the walls failing in flexure tend to control the design of a building; ii) the influence of ALR is relatively small on the drift capacities of walls failing in shear; computing a mean and CoV over the entire ALR seems therefore justifiable.

Figure 10 shows the drift capacity of all walls as a function of ALR and failure mode using three different normalisations. These are:

- $\delta_u \cdot l_{\text{wall}} / h_0$ (Figure 10b, normalisation adopted by EC8-Part 3 [2] for the drift capacity of walls failing in flexure);
- $\delta_u \cdot h_{\text{wall}} / h_0$ (Figure 10c, normalisation adopted in [8], [12], [19]);
- $\delta_u \cdot \min(l_{\text{wall}}, h_{\text{wall}}) / h_0$ (Figure 10d, normalisation adopted in [7]).

The same plots are shown for HC walls only in Figure 11. The figures show that the normalisation does not reduce the scatter. This is partly due to the fact that most walls were tested under a shear span to height ratio (h_0/h_{wall}) of 0.5 (Figure 9). The database contains a good distribution of shear span ratios (h_0/l_{wall}) (Figure 8) but the normalisation with the shear span ratio does not reduce the scatter.

The finding that normalising the drift capacity does not reduce the scatter is not in line with mechanical and numerical studies nor the trends observed in some isolated test series: Mechanical (Eq. 13 in [11]), numerical [10], some empirical models [8], [12], [19] as well as tests [14], [19], [28] suggest that the shear span ratio or the shear span to wall height ratio influences the drift capacity. For this reason, normalising the drift capacity by the shear span should be considered. Previous works [8], [12], [19]. showed that for some test series normalising the drift capacity nearly eliminates the difference in drift capacity for walls failing in shear or flexure (e.g. PUP-Series [8] that was tested with shear spans between $h_0=0.5-1.5 h_{\text{wall}}$). This finding also holds for stone masonry walls [6] where, consequently, one single drift capacity model can be used.

Should the drift capacity be a function of the failure mode?

The data presented in Figure 10-Figure 11 indicates that the drift capacity should be a function of the failure mode if the drift capacity is not normalised. If it is normalised, the differences reduces but do not diminish for $ALR < 0.15$. This is in line with Figure 5 of the recent study in [11]. Note, that making the drift capacity a function of the failure mode, requires that the failure

mode can be predicted correctly. This aspect is addressed in Section 9. The final draft of the new version of EC8-Part 3 [29] contains a proposal for predicting also these hybrid failure modes. Its performance for modern masonry walls is also tested in Section 9.

Based on these findings, and similarly to what was done for the stone masonry walls in [6], two drift capacity models will be proposed. Both models differentiate between various unit types. In the first model the drift capacities depend also on the failure mode (the ALR is only introduced to differentiate between walls that are subjected to a normal range of ALRs and those that are subjected to very high ALRs). In the second model the drift capacities do not depend on the failure mode, but in addition to the unit type also on the ALR and shear span to height ratio.

Figure 10: All walls: Drift capacity and normalised drift capacity as a function of the axial load ratio and the failure mode.

Figure 11: HC walls only: Drift capacity and normalised drift capacity as a function of the axial load ratio and the failure mode.

Figure 12: Drift capacity for the four unit materials for which more than 10 entries are retained (HC, SB, CS, AAC, LAC).

5.1 File register

fig_normalisation_1.m	Figure 10 a-d
fig_normalisation_1_HC.m	Figure 11 a-d
fig_failure_mode_4.m	Figure 12 a-e

6 Influence of the aspect ratio of the wall on the drift capacity

Should the drift capacity be a function of the aspect ratio of the wall?

Figure 13 shows that the aspect ratio has no notable influence on the drift capacity. This applies to both walls failing in shear and in flexure. The drift capacity models should therefore not be a function of the aspect ratios of the walls.

Figure 13: Drift capacity as a function of the axial load ratio and the aspect ratio

6.1 File register

fig_aspect_ratio_2.m	Figure 13 a+b
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7 Influence of the void ratio and unit class on the drift capacity

Should the drift capacity be a function of the void ratio or the unit class?

The unit classes according to EC6 [30] are determined based on the volume of all holes, the web and shell thicknesses and the unit material (Table 2). Group 1-3 have vertical holes, group 4 horizontal holes. None of the test units in the database belongs to Group 4. In the database, the volume percentage of holes, for those walls for which this value has been specified, varies between 0% (solid bricks) and 54%. Figure 14a shows the drift capacity for different groups of void ratios and Figure 14b for the three unit groups. The influence of the unit groups does not seem strong; if the results are plotted for different void ratios, it seems that hollow units lead to smaller drift capacities than solid units. Note that not all test units were assigned a unit group or a void ratio; for this reason plotting one or the other does not lead to the same plot. This

becomes more evident if walls failing in shear and flexure are plotted separately (Figure 15). However, the data base is not sufficient to differentiate between walls of different void ratios. For a single unit type, only a narrow distribution of void ratios exist (Figure 16a), which does not allow identification of a trend of the drift capacity with the void ratio. Figure 16a shows the drift capacity as a function of the void ratio for HC walls and SB walls (assuming that the latter are mainly clay bricks). However, it does not lead to any further insights and only shows that SB walls lead to larger drifts than HC walls.

The data only allows to differentiate between solid bricks and hollow bricks. Most of the solid brick walls are clay brick walls. For this typology, a drift capacity larger than for the other walls seems justifiable.

Figure 14: Drift capacity as a function of the axial load ratio and the void ratio (a) and EC6 unit group (b).

Figure 15: Drift capacity as a function of the axial load ratio and the void ratio for walls failing in shear (a) and walls failing in flexure (b).

Figure 16: Distribution of void ratios within the database for the various unit types (a) and drift capacity as a function of the void ratio for HC and SB walls (b).

Table 2: Geometrical requirements for grouping of masonry units according to Eurocode 6 [30]

	Materials and limits for masonry units										
	Group 1S (all materials) ^a	Group 1 (all materials) ^a	Units	Group 2				Group 3		Group 4	
				Vertical holes				Horizontal holes			
Volume of all holes (% of the gross volume)	≤ 5	≤ 25	clay	> 25; ≤ 55		> 25; ≤ 70		> 25; ≤ 70		> 25; ≤ 70	
			calcium silicate	> 25; ≤ 55		not used		not used		not used	
			concrete ^b	> 25; ≤ 60		> 25; ≤ 70		> 25; ≤ 50		> 25; ≤ 50	
Volume of any hole (% of the gross volume)	No requirement	≤ 12.5	clay	each of multiple holes ≤ 2 gripholes up to a total of 12.5		each of multiple holes ≤ 2 gripholes up to a total of 12.5		each of multiple holes ≤ 30		each of multiple holes ≤ 30	
			calcium silicate	each of multiple holes ≤ 15 gripholes up to a total of 30		not used		not used		not used	
			concrete ^b	each of multiple holes ≤ 30 gripholes up to a total of 30		each of multiple holes ≤ 30 gripholes up to a total of 30		each of multiple holes ≤ 25		each of multiple holes ≤ 25	
Declared values of thickness of webs and shells (mm)	No requirement	No requirement		web	shell	web	shell	web	shell	web	shell
			clay	≥ 5	≥ 8	≥ 3	≥ 6	≥ 5	≥ 6	≥ 5	≥ 6
			calcium silicate	≥ 5	≥ 10	not used		not used		not used	
Declared value of combined thickness of webs and shells (% of the overall width)	No requirement	No requirement	clay	≥ 16		≥ 12		≥ 12		≥ 12	
			calcium silicate	≥ 20		not used		not used		not used	
			concrete ^b	≥ 18		≥ 15		≥ 45		≥ 45	
			^a Group 1 and 1S units may contain indentations, for example frogs, gripholes or grooves in the bed face, if such indentations are to be filled with mortar in the finished wall.								
			^b In the case of conical holes, or cellular holes, use the mean value of the thickness of the webs and the shells.								

7.1 File register

fig_void_ratio_1.m	Figure 14 a
fig_unit_group_1.m	Figure 14 b
fig_void_ratio_2.m	Figure 15 a
fig_void_ratio_3.m	Figure 15 b
fig_distribution_void_ratio_1.m	Figure 16 a
fig_void_ratio_4.m	Figure 16 b

8 Influence of bed joints, head joints and mortar type on the drift capacity

Should the drift capacity be a function of the mortar type and of the type of head joints?

In order to eliminate the influence of the unit type on the drift capacity, in this section only walls with HC units are considered. The walls are grouped in walls that fail in shear and walls that fail in a hybrid or flexural mode. Figure 17 shows that walls built with general purpose mortar (GP) and thin bed mortar (TL) reach similar capacities for shear and flexural failures; for light-weight mortar data is not available. Also the influence of the type of the head joint seems rather small on the drift capacity: Figure 18 shows the drift capacity for head joints that are filled, head joints with mortar pockets and head joints that are unfilled and with or without tongue and groove.

The number of available data points is rather limited; the findings therefore not yet very well supported. However, the available data does not suggest that the mortar type or the type of the head joint has a significant influence on the drift capacity and therefore it is suggested that the empirical drift capacity models will not account for these two parameters.

Figure 17: Influence of the bed joint type for hollow core clay bricks for walls with shear failure (left) and walls with mixed or flexural failure (right).

Figure 18: Influence of the head joint type for hollow core clay bricks for walls with shear failure (a) and walls with mixed or flexural failure (b).

8.1 File register

fig_bed_and_head_joint_2.m	Figure 17
fig_bed_and_head_joint_1.m	Figure 18

9 Prediction of failure modes

If the failure mode is to be a parameter of the drift capacity, it is important that it can be predicted correctly. Morandi et al. [5] analysed to which extent the failure mode can be predicted for the 135 walls in their database with a height of at least 1.5 m and at least 8 courses (note that there is a large overlap between the database by Morandi et al. and the European database). For 4 out of these 135 walls the observed failure mode is not known and for one the predicted failure mode cannot be computed (unknown shear span). Therefore, for 130 walls the predicted failure mode can be compared to the observed one. Morandi et al. [5] differentiate between 3 shear failure modes (“shear”, “sliding”, “gaping”; the latter refers to a shear failure that involves mainly opening of the head and bed joints), 1 flexural failure mode and several hybrid modes.

Using the shear and flexural resistances given in Morandi et al. [5], the predicted failure mode (shear or flexure) was compared against the observed one (shear, flexure or hybrid). Table 3 shows this comparison. When all failure modes are predicted correctly, all off-diagonal terms are zero. However, since hybrid modes cannot be predicted with this approach, some errors necessarily result. If the drift capacity model comprises two models, one for walls failing in shear and one for walls failing in a hybrid or flexural mode, then it is particularly important to avoid the prediction of false-positive flexural failure when shear failure is observed, as this is likely to lead to an unconservative drift estimate. Table 3 shows that false-positive for flexural failure are only obtained for a minority of walls (2%). Note that a similar study for stone masonry walls (Figure 13a in [6]) led to less favourable findings; for 25% of the stone masonry walls that failed in shear, a flexural failure was predicted.

The final draft of EC8-Part 3 [29] puts forward the introduction of a hybrid failure mode. A wall is assumed to fail in a hybrid mode, if the difference between the resistance of the shear and flexural resistance is less than 10%. Table 4 shows the new distribution. If a hybrid or flexural

failure mode is predicted but a shear failure is observed, the drift estimate is likely to be unconservative. As several walls are predicted to fail in a hybrid mode but failed in fact in shear, the percentage of a priori unconservative cases has increased from 2% to 14% when introducing the new failure mode “hybrid”.

Table 3: Database by Morandi et al. [5]: Predicted vs observed failure mode (this table reproduces Figure 16 in Morandi et al. Small differences were obtained, which do not, however, influence the conclusions.

# of tests	Shear - observed	Hybrid - observed	Flexural - observed
Shear - predicted	73 (58%)	27 (21%)	12 (8%)
Hybrid - predicted	0	0	0
Flexural - predicted	3 (2%)	8 (6%)	7 (5%)

Table 4: Database by Morandi et al. [5]: Predicted vs observed failure mode if the notion of a hybrid failure mode is introduced in the prediction according to the final draft of EC8-Part 3 [29].

# of tests	Shear - observed	Hybrid - observed	Flexural - observed
Shear - predicted	59 (45%)	17 (13%)	2 (2%)
Hybrid - predicted	16 (12%)	13 (10%)	15 (11%)
Flexural - predicted	2 (2%)	5 (4%)	2 (2%)

9.1 File register

Read_Excel_file_Morandi_et_al.m Output variable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • failure_mode_pred_vs_observed • failure_mode_pred_vs_observed_norm 	Table 3
Read_Excel_file_Morandi_et_al.m Output variable: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • failure_mode_pred_vs_observed_incl_hybrid • failure_mode_pred_vs_observed_incl_hybrid_norm 	Table 4

10 Ratio drift at maximum force and drift at axial load failure to ultimate drift capacity

To associate the ultimate drift capacity with a certain limit state, this section investigates the ratio between the drift at maximum force and the drift at axial load failure to the ultimate drift. In many previous works, the ultimate drift capacity (drift at 20% drop in force) is associated with the NC limit state (e.g. [8], [11], [31]). The very recent work associates the ultimate drift capacity with the SD limit state [5]. This section revisits the topic. It starts with a review of definitions of limit state drifts for other construction materials.

10.1 Definitions of limit state drifts for other construction materials

For reinforced concrete (RC) structural elements, the final draft of EC8, Part 3 [29] states that the ultimate chord rotation is associated to the deformation capacity at 80% of the peak strength (Paragraph 8.4.2.2.2 (1)):

“The end of an element should be considered to have reached its ultimate chord rotation (or cyclic chord rotation capacity), θ_u , if the element’s lateral force resistance drops below 80% of its peak value.”

The deformation capacities of RC structural elements in EC8, Part 3 [29] are largely based on the work by Grammatikou et al. [32]. In [32], it is specified that the ultimate chord rotation θ_u corresponds to a drop in force by 20% but details on the post-processing of the experimental results are not given.

10.2 Ratio of drift capacity at maximum force to ultimate drift capacity

The current EC8-Part 3 [2] assumes that the ratio of the drift capacity at the limit state SD to NC is 3/4. The final draft of the new EC8-Part 3 [29] assumes that the ratio of θ_w / θ_{u2} corresponds also to 3/4 (Paragraph 11.4.1.2(3)). Figure 19 shows that this ratio corresponds rather well to the ratio of the drift at maximum force to the ultimate drift. The same observation holds for stone masonry [6].

Figure 19: Ratio of the drift capacity at maximum force to the ultimate drift capacity (line represents here the moving median, not the moving mean)

10.3 Ratio of drift capacity at axial load failure to ultimate drift capacity

How far is the wall away from collapse when it reaches δ_u ?

Figure 20 shows the ratio of the maximum recorded drift to the ultimate drift. The maximum recorded drift is taken as a proxy of the drift at axial load failure δ_c . Most tests were not tested up to axial load failure and the drifts can therefore only be taken as a proxy. A test series where testing continued up to axial load failure is the PUP-series [14]. For this series, the ratio of δ_c / δ_u is between 1.0 and 1.3 with half the tests having ratios very close to 1.0. Figure 20 shows that the ratio of δ_c / δ_u is often rather close to 1.0. An exception are some HC walls that were tested under relatively low axial load ratios. For these walls, the ratio of δ_c / δ_u reaches for several test units values between 1.5 and 2.5.

Figure 20: Ratio of the maximum recorded drift capacity to the ultimate drift capacity (line represents here the moving median, not the moving mean). Solid markers: Data from the European Database. Empty markers: Data from Morandi et al. [5]. The moving median is based on the solid markers.

10.4 To which LS does the ultimate drift capacity correspond?

Definitions of LS in EC8

The limit state definitions in the new version of the EC8, Part 1 [33] are the following:

- “LS of Near Collapse (NC) shall be defined as one in which the structure is heavily damaged, with large permanent drifts, but retains its vertical-load bearing capacity; most non-structural components, where present, have collapsed.”
- “LS of Significant Damage (SD) shall be defined as one in which the structure is significantly damaged, possibly with moderate permanent drifts but retains its vertical-load bearing capacity; non-structural components, where present, are damaged (e.g., partitions and infills have not yet failed out-of-plane). The structure is expected to be repairable, but in some cases, it may be uneconomic to repair.”

New buildings are designed for LS SD (EC8, Part 1 [33]) while the assessment of existing buildings is based on the LS NC (EC8, Part 3 [29]). For masonry elements, EC8, Part 3 [29] gives a detailed piece-wise linear force-deformation envelope. In this envelope (Fig. 11.1 in [29]), the chord rotation

- θ_u corresponds to the limit when the element still retains its vertical-load bearing capacity but lost a certain percentage of strength with regard to the peak strength;
- θ_{u2} corresponds to the limit when the element still retains its vertical-load bearing capacity but the lateral strength drops further. It is assumed that the wall maintains a residual strength after this limit state. For walls with regular masonry, this residual strength corresponds to 90% and 50% for walls failing in flexure and shear respectively. There is no ultimate chord rotation capacity at which the lateral and/or axial strength drops to zero.

It assumes that the ratio of θ_{u2}/θ_u corresponds to 4/3, which is equal to the ratio between the drift capacities at NC and SD LS in the previous version of EC8, Part 3 [2].

Does δ_u derived in this report correspond to θ_u or θ_{u2} in EC8, Part 3?

It is here assumed that the ultimate drift as defined in this report corresponds to the chord rotation θ_{u2} as defined in the final draft of the new EC8, Part 3 [29]. To recall, the definition of the ultimate drift adopted in this report was given by Equation (5):

$$\delta_u = \max(\delta_u^+, \delta_u^-) \quad (5)$$

where δ_u^+ and δ_u^- are the drift values that correspond to a 20% drop in strength of the force-displacement envelopes in the positive and negative loading direction (only one envelope is defined that envelopes all cycles).

This does not follow the proposal in the recent publication by Morandi et al. [5]. However, it takes up the idea that the definition of the ultimate drift capacity according to Equation (1) leads to a limit state that is not yet close to collapse. By changing the definition of the ultimate drift from Equation (1)

$$\delta_u = \min(\delta_{u,1}^+, \delta_{u,1}^-, \delta_{u,2}^+, \delta_{u,2}^-, \delta_{u,3}^+, \delta_{u,3}^-) \quad (1)$$

to that of Equation (5), this conservatism is at least partly removed.

Association of δ_u with the NC limit state is based on the following reasons:

- The ratio between the drift at axial load failure (here approximated as the maximum recorded drift) and the ultimate drift as defined in Equation (5) is for most walls close to unity. An exception are HC walls subjected to axial load ratios < 0.10 . For such walls the association of δ_u with the NC limit state might indeed seem conservative.

- The adopted definition is in line with the definition adopted for RC elements, for which δ_u is also associated with NC.
- If it is assumed that the ratio of θ_{u2}/θ_u equals 4/3, i.e., if it is assumed that $\theta_u = 0.75\theta_{u2}$, it is found that θ_u corresponds approximately to the drift at peak force. At this instant, damage localisation starts and further damage is concentrated in one major crack rather than in a distributed crack pattern. At this instant, the integrity of the wall can be jeopardised (in particular for walls with high axial load ratios).
- Equation (1) requires that the wall passes almost three entire cycles at its ultimate drift capacity. This is rather severe; in particular as the number of cycles applied in quasi-static cyclic tests are typically considerably higher than the number of cycles URM buildings are subjected in real buildings [34], [35].

11 Drift capacity model 1: Drift capacity as a function of the failure mode and the unit typology

The objective of the drift capacity models proposed in this chapter and the next is to strike a good balance between accuracy, simplicity and our insights into the drift capacity of URM walls from numerical and mechanical models, which—most likely due to the limited size of the dataset—are often not reflected in the data.

This section proposes a drift capacity model where the drift capacity is a function of the failure mode. Based on the analysis presented in the previous section, this section proposes a drift capacity model, which has the following characteristics:

- The drift capacities are determined for each unit typology, for which more than 10 data points are available for walls that fail in shear. These are: HC, SB, CS and AAC. For LAC, only one wall fails in shear and therefore no separate drift capacity is defined.
- The statistical evaluation focuses on the walls failing in shear. For the walls failing in a hybrid of flexural mode, the drift capacity will be set as a multiple of the drift capacity in shear. This approach will be less accurate but simpler than tabulating also for walls failing in flexure unit specific drift capacities.
- Void ratio, unit class, bed and head joints are not considered as the data base is not sufficient to identify clear trends (apart from the difference between solid and hollow bricks).
- Shear span and aspect ratio are not considered because using a normalised drift capacity does not reduce the scatter.
- The ALR is not considered in the model because the trend with ALR is small for walls failing in shear. However, the derived drift capacity model is only valid for $ALR \leq 0.3$ as most tests were carried out with ALR between 0 and 0.3.
- It is assumed that the ultimate drift capacity corresponds to the drift at NC limit state and that the ratio of the drifts at NC and SD is 4/3.

11.1 Statistical evaluation

Table 5 shows the statistical evaluation of the drift capacities of walls failing in shear for unit typologies HC, SB, CS and AAC. Figure 21 shows the distribution of the drift capacities, once as distribution curve and once as box plot. The central mark indicates the median, and box extends from the 25th to 75th [36]. The whiskers extend to the most extreme data points not considered outliers, and the outliers are plotted individually using the '+' symbol [36]. The notches indicate the confidence interval of the median. If the notches of two boxes do not overlap, the true median of the two groups differs with 95% confidence [36]. Apart from the SB

walls, the confidence intervals of all unit typologies overlap. However, the overlap is not very large and although the confidence that the median drift capacities differ is not 95% it is proposed that different drift capacities are specified for HC, CS and AAC walls.

Table 5: Statics of drift capacity for walls failing in shear

	# of tests	Min(δ_u)	5%ile	50%ile	50%ile/5%ile	σ	CoV
		[%]	[%]	[%]		[%]	
HC	41	0.13	0.19	0.31	1.64	0.10	0.31
SB	15	0.24	0.38	0.69	1.82	0.28	0.38
CS	11	0.18	0.13	0.28	2.13	0.15	0.49
AAC	19	0.14	0.20	0.37	1.90	0.16	0.41

Figure 21: Distribution of drift capacities for walls failing in shear

11.2 Drift capacities for walls failing in shear

Traditionally, the drift capacities are specified for the limit state SD and the drifts at NC computed as fixed ratio [2]. This approach is also followed in the final draft of EC8-Part 3 [29] and will therefore also be adopted here. The drift capacities at the SD limit state δ_{SD} are defined as $\frac{3}{4}$ times the 50%ile value of the ultimate drift capacity δ_u :

$$\delta_{SD}^{shear} = \frac{3}{4} \cdot \delta_{u,50\%}^{shear} \quad (6)$$

The values are rounded to the nearest 0.05. The drift capacity at the NC limit state δ_{NC} is determined as:

$$\delta_{NC}^{shear} = \frac{4}{3} \cdot \delta_{SD}^{shear} \quad (7)$$

The drift capacity at NC limit state therefore corresponds to the ultimate drift capacity as defined in this report. The drift capacities are limited to walls with $ALR \leq 0.3$ because (i) only very few tests are available for these ALRs; (ii) Although the available database shows for

shear failures no trend with the ALR, our mechanical understanding and the investigation of individual test series shows that not only the deformation capacity of walls failing in a hybrid or a flexural mode but also the deformation capacity of walls failing in shear reduces with ALR (see Section 5). Walls with larger ALR should be avoided as their failure might be very brittle. If this is not possible, it should be assumed that walls with $ALR > 0.3$ have only one third of the drift capacities for walls with $ALR \leq 0.3$. To avoid a jump in drift capacities at $ALR=0.3$, it is recommended to use Model 2 instead. For unit materials, for which no drift limit was specified, it is recommended to use the drift limit of the unit, which is expected to lead to a similar response. Recommended values for LAC and SB-CS are given in Section 14.2.

Table 6: Recommended drift limits for URM walls failing in shear with $ALR \leq 0.3$

	SD drift limit δ_{SD}^{shear} [%]	NC drift limit δ_{NC}^{shear} [%]
HC	0.25	0.33
SB	0.50	0.67
CS	0.20	0.27
AAC	0.30	0.40

11.3 Drift capacities for walls failing in flexure

The drift capacity model for walls failing in flexure is considered less critical than the drift capacity model for walls failing in shear because the deformation capacity of a building is typically controlled by the walls failing in shear.

For simplicity, it is here recommended to specify for the walls failing in a hybrid or flexural mode, a drift capacity twice the drift capacity of walls failing in shear. This recommendation is based on the observation that most walls failing in shear were tested under double-bending and flexural failure was mostly obtained for walls tested as cantilever walls.

$$\delta_{SD}^{flex} = 2.0 \cdot \delta_{SD}^{shear} \quad (8)$$

$$\delta_{NC}^{flex} = 2.0 \cdot \delta_{NC}^{shear} \quad (9)$$

11.4 Ratio of predicted to experimentally determined drift capacities

Figure 22 and Figure 23 show the ratio of predicted to experimentally determined drift capacities for Model 1. The predicted drift capacities are NC limit state drift capacities; the experimentally determined drift capacities are the ultimate drifts δ_u . Figure 22 shows that the model is more accurate for walls failing in shear than in a hybrid or flexural mode. This is expected as the model was calibrated for walls failing in shear.

Figure 22: Model 1: Ratio of predicted to experimentally determined drift capacities for walls failing in shear (a) and walls failing in a hybrid or flexural failure mode (b). The figure assumes that the failure modes can be correctly predicted.

Figure 23: Model 1: Ratio of predicted to experimentally determined drift capacities for the various unit typologies as a function of the axial load ratio. The figure assumes that the failure modes can be correctly predicted.

11.5 File register

fig_drift_capacity_shear_2.m • Variable: output_matrix	Table 5
fig_drift_capacity_shear_2.m	Figure 21 a
fig_drift_capacity_shear_1.m	Figure 21 b
fig_ratio_observed_predicted_1.m	Figure 22, n_model=1
fig_ratio_observed_predicted_2.m	Figure 23, n_model=1

12 Drift capacity model 2: Drift capacity as a function of ALR, shear span and unit typology

Building on previous works, in particular the first drift capacity model of this kind in [12], a drift capacity model is proposed that is not a function of the failure mode, but instead of the ALR, the shear span to height ratio and the unit typology. For simplicity, the model is expressed as the drift capacities for walls failing in shear of Model 1, which are tabulated in Table 6.

$$\delta_{SD}^{flex \& shear} = 7 \cdot \delta_{SD}^{shear(M1)} \cdot \frac{h_0}{h_{wall}} \cdot \left(0.4 - \frac{\sigma_0}{f_u}\right) \quad (10)$$

$$\delta_{NC}^{flex \& shear} = \frac{4}{3} \cdot \delta_{SD}^{flex \& shear} \quad (11)$$

Note that the shear span and the axial load ratio vary during seismic loading. For the drift capacity assessment, the shear span and the axial load at the point of failure must be considered. This means that in a numerical simulation the drift capacity of the wall must be continuously updated.

12.1 Ratio of predicted to experimentally determined drift capacities

Figure 24 and Figure 25 shows the performance of Model 2 by plotting the ratio of the predicted to experimentally observed drift capacities. As for Model 1, the predicted drift capacities are NC limit state drift capacities; the experimentally determined drift capacities are the ultimate drifts δ_u . The model performance is not as good as the performance of Model 1. However, it reflects better the influence of the ALR and the shear span, which are known from numerical and mechanical studies as well as isolated experimental studies, but which are not reflected in the data set (see discussion in Section 5).

Figure 24: Model 2: Ratio of predicted to experimentally determined drift capacities for walls failing in shear (a) and walls failing in a hybrid or flexural failure mode (b). The figure assumes that the failure modes can be correctly predicted.

Figure 25: Model 2: Ratio of predicted to experimentally determined drift capacities for the various unit typologies as a function of the axial load ratio. The figure assumes that the failure modes can be correctly predicted.

12.2 File register

fig_ratio_observed_predicted_1.m	Figure 24, n_model=3;
fig_ratio_observed_predicted_2.m	Figure 25, n_model=3;

13 Drift capacity model 3: Drift capacity as a function of ALR, failure mode and unit typology

Based on discussions within WG1, with the goal of eliminating the jump in the drift capacity model 1 with the ALR and to improve numerical stability of models, which use the drift capacity model as an input, this third drift capacity model is a function of failure mode, ALR, and the unit typology. Note, however, that this does not fully eliminate the possibility of a jump in drift capacity from one analysis step to the next because the model is failure mode dependent. If the wall is predicted to fail at time step i in flexure and in time step $i+1$ in shear, the drift capacity decreases from time step i to $i+1$ by (approximately) a factor of two. This problem can only be solved if a drift capacity model of the form of Model 2 is adopted (i.e. a drift capacity model that is *not* a function of the failure mode).

The drift capacity model proposed here is the following:

$$\delta_{SD}^{shear} = 6.67 \cdot \delta_{SD}^{shear(M1)} \cdot \left(0.35 - \frac{\sigma_0}{f_u}\right) \quad (12)$$

$$\delta_{NC}^{shear} = \frac{4}{3} \cdot \delta_{SD}^{shear} \quad (13)$$

whereas δ_{SD}^{shear} is not larger than 1.0 and not smaller than 1/3.

As for Model 1, it is assumed that walls failing in flexure have twice the drift capacity of walls failing in shear:

$$\delta_{SD}^{flex} = 2.0 \cdot \delta_{SD}^{shear} \quad (14)$$

$$\delta_{NC}^{flex} = 2.0 \cdot \delta_{NC}^{shear} \quad (15)$$

13.1 Ratio of predicted to experimentally determined drift capacities

Figure 24 and Figure 25 shows the performance of Model 2 by plotting the ratio of the predicted to experimentally observed drift capacities. As for Model 1, the predicted drift capacities are NC limit state drift capacities; the experimentally determined drift capacities are the ultimate drifts δ_u . The model performance is not as good as the performance of Model 1. However, it reflects better the influence of the ALR and the shear span, which are known from numerical and mechanical studies as well as isolated experimental studies, but which are not reflected in the data set (see discussion in Section 5).

Figure 26: Model 3: Ratio of predicted to experimentally determined drift capacities for walls failing in shear (a) and walls failing in a hybrid or flexural failure mode (b). The figure assumes that the failure modes can be correctly predicted.

Figure 27: Model 3: Ratio of predicted to experimentally determined drift capacities for the various unit typologies as a function of the axial load ratio. The figure assumes that the failure modes can be correctly predicted.

13.2 File register

06_Drift_capacity_model_Feb_2022/fig_ratio_observed_predicted_1.m	Figure 26, n_model=4;
06_Drift_capacity_model_Feb_2022/fig_ratio_observed_predicted_2.m	Figure 27, n_model=4;

14 Conclusions and recommendations

This objective of this report was to put forward drift capacity models for the revised Eurocode 8, Part 3 (EC8-Part 3). For this purpose, it reviews the data available on quasi-static cyclic tests on masonry walls in the recently assembled European database for URM walls. Based on this review, it proposes two simple drift capacity models. Both models account for the unit typology. In addition, Model 1 accounts for the failure mode and follows therefore the traditional

form for URM drift capacity models. Unlike the current drift capacity model in the current EC8-Part 3 [2], it introduces an axial load ratio limit of 0.3. Walls subjected to higher ALR should be avoided; if this is not possible, it should be assumed that they have only one third of the drift capacity of walls with $ALR \leq 0.3$. Alternatively, in order to avoid a sudden jump in drift capacities at $ALR=0.3$, it is recommended to use Model 2 (see below). Note that the idea of an ALR-limit is already included in the German national annex to Eurocode 8 [37] for walls failing in shear. It limits the SD drift capacity of 0.4%, which is specified in the current EC8-Part 3, to walls with an $ALR \leq 0.15$. For walls with a larger ALR, the drift capacity is reduced to 0.3%.

Model 2 does not consider the failure mode but the ALR and shear span. When compared to the experimental data, the bias and scatter associated with Model 2 is somewhat larger than that of Model 1. However, it reflects better our understanding of the mechanical response of URM walls. Note that Model 2 depends on the ALR and the shear span, which vary for each wall and also during the loading. Model 1 might therefore be easier to apply in numerical simulations.

Neither of the two models accounts for the influence of the void ratio, unit class, bed and head joints and mortar type. The database was not sufficient to quantify the influence of these parameters. The following sections compare the proposed drift capacity models to the drift limits for modern masonry that are included in the final draft of EC8-Part 3 and the drift limits derived by Morandi et al. [5].

14.1 Comparisons with drift limits for modern masonry in the final draft of EC8-Part 3

The drift limits that are included in the final draft of EC8-Part 3 [29] for modern masonry are summarised in Table 7 and compared to the drift capacity models proposed in this report. It shows that the drift capacities in the final draft of EC8-Part 3 [29] are—with the exception of drifts for flexural failures under small ALRs—larger than those proposed by Model 1 and 2. The comparison is visualised in Figure 28.

Note that the definition of the chord rotation θ used in EC8-Part 3 [29] is somewhat different to the drift definition used here. The drift was defined as the horizontal top displacement divided by the wall height. The chord rotation in EC8-Part 3 is defined as follows:

$$\theta_i = r_i + \frac{u_0 - u_1}{H_i} \quad (16)$$

where r_i is the rotation at the end of the element where the resistance is reached¹, u_0 the transversal displacement at the contraflexure point, u_i , the transversal displacement at the end section and H_i the distance between the contraflexure point and the end section. For most wall tests, the displacement at the height of contraflexure is not known (with the exception of tests that were conducted as cantilever tests). For double-bending and cantilever tests the two definition lead to the same results (assuming ideal symmetric behaviour and zero top and bottom rotation in the case of double-bending).

Table 7: Comparison of drift limits for modern masonry

	Drift capacities in the final draft of EC8-Part 3 [29] for modern masonry	Drift capacities δ_{SD} proposed in this report	
	θ_u	Model 1	Model 2
Flexural failure	$1\% \cdot (1-ALR)$	$0.4 - 1.0\%^{1)}$	

¹ For flexural failure, the section where the resistance is reached first is clear. However, for shear failure, the resistance should be reached at the same time at the two ends of the element (unless the selfweight and therefore the change in axial force throughout the wall is accounted for).

		for ALR > 0.3: 0.13-0.33%	(1.4-3.5%)·h ₀ /h _{wall} ·(0.4-ALR)
Shear failure			
Solid brick masonry	0.6-0.8% ²⁾	0.5%	
Hollow units	0.35% - 0.8% ²⁾	0.2-0.35% ¹⁾	

- 1) Depending on masonry typology
- 2) Depending on failure mode in shear (sliding, sliding controlled by unit strength, diagonal cracking)

Figure 28: Comparison of drift capacity models for the SD limit state for modern masonry in the final draft of EC8-Part 3 [29] to the two models proposed in this report. The coloured areas refer to ranges of drift capacities that result because the model accounts for various shear failure types (EC8-Part 3) or brick types (Model 1 and 2).

14.2 Comparisons with drift limits in Morandi et al.

Morandi et al. [5] analysed a data set of equal size to the data set analysed in this report. The two data sets were not identical but overlapped to a large extent. The main differences between the two works are the following:

- The ultimate drift capacity, which is associated to the 20% drop in strength, is defined differently (see Section 3.1). Morandi et al. [5] defined for each cycle number ($n=1-3$) and loading direction (positive and negative) a separate envelope, computed for each of these envelopes the drift associated with a 20% drop in strength and defined the ultimate drift capacity as the *minimum* of the six envelopes. In this report, only the envelope of all cycles is defined and the drift associated with a drop in strength of 20% extracted for the positive and the negative loading direction. The ultimate drift is taken as the *maximum* value of the two.
- Morandi et al. [5] proposes that the ultimate drift corresponds to the SD limit drift, while in this report the ultimate drift is associated with the NC limit drift. For the NC limit drift, Morandi et al. [5] propose to take the largest drift applied in the test, for which all cycles were completed.

Though the definitions of the drifts for the NC limit state adopted in Morandi et al. [5] and here are therefore different, the resulting drift capacities for walls failing in shear are very similar (Table 8). For this reason, it is recommended to use the values given in Morandi et al. for the two unit types LAC and SB-CS for which this report did not derive a drift capacity due to lack

of data. The corresponding drift capacities at the SD limit state, rounded to the nearest 0.05%, are:

- LAC: $\delta_{SD}^{\text{shear}} = 0.25\%$
- SB-CS: $\delta_{SD}^{\text{shear}} = 0.20\%$

Table 8: Comparison of drift capacities for the NC limit state in Morandi et al. [5] and in Model 1 (Table 6). The values from Morandi et al. [5] correspond to the median values.

	Morandi et al. $\theta_{\max,f}$ [%]	Model 1 $\delta_{NC}^{\text{shear}}$ [%]
HC	0.32	0.33
SB (Morandi et al. SB-C)	0.50	0.67
CS	0.26	0.27
AAC	0.36	0.40
LAC	0.32	
SB-CS	0.25	

14.3 Recommendations for future work

- Include tests that are contained in the database by Morandi et al. but not yet in the European database.
- Investigate whether the approach proposed for modern masonry in the final draft of EC8-Part 3 improves the prediction of drift capacities (also for stone masonry).
- Differentiate between experimentally determined compressive strength and characteristic compressive strength? Neglecting the difference is, however, conservative.

14.4 File register

06_Drift_capacity_model_Feb_2022/fig_comparison_drift_capacity_models.m	Figure 28b
06_Drift_capacity_model_Feb_2022/fig_comparison_drift_capacity_models_2.m	Figure 28a

15 References

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16 Annex: Extracts from the final draft of EC8-Part 3

11.3.2 Modelling of global in-plane response of masonry walls

11.3.2.1 Force-deformation relationship for masonry structural elements

(1) In the case of linear elastic analysis, the stiffness of the primary seismic elements should be calculated considering the effect of cracking (EN 1998-1:20xx, **5.3.1.3**) and should be based on the secant value at 70% of the ultimate strength of the element. Unless a more accurate analysis of the cracked elements is performed, the elastic flexural and shear stiffness properties of masonry elements may be taken as a fraction of the corresponding stiffness of the uncracked element, according to EN 1998-1:2004, **9.4(3)**.

NOTE The use of cracked or uncracked stiffness can be driven by the results of preliminary analysis (5.4.2), if it is carried out.

(2) In the case of nonlinear analysis, according to EN 1998-1:xxx, **4.2.2(3)**, proper piecewise linear force-deformation relationships should be defined at element level, in terms of shear force and element drift ratio. The elastic stiffness should correspond to cracked conditions. Trilinear force–deformation relationships, which consider pre-cracking and post-cracking stiffnesses, may be used.

(3) In masonry buildings, the progressive strength degradation should be included at element level, in order to evaluate the ultimate displacement capacity at global level by considering the progressive damage and failure under seismic (horizontal) and gravity (vertical) loads of all resisting walls; in this case safety verification should be made in global terms (6.7.3.3). If the progressive strength degradation is not included in the model, the nonlinear analysis should consider verification in local (element-level) terms (6.7.3.2).

(4) A piecewise linear relationship should be used to describe the progressive strength degradation. Three damage levels should be defined in terms of drift thresholds at element level, which are structurally relevant points along the force-deformation relationship (Figure 11.1), as given in a) to c).

- a) yielding drift θ_y , corresponding to the attainment of the maximum shear strength;
- b) ultimate drift θ_u , corresponding to a drop in the shear force with respect to the peak value (by an amount that depends on the failure mechanism);
- c) second ultimate drift θ_{u2} , wherein the shear force is further reduced (by an amount that depends on the failure mechanism) with respect to the maximum shear resistance.

NOTE Quantitative values for the above-mentioned parameters of the force-deformation relationship, for piers and spandrels under different conditions, are provided in 11.4.1.2.

(5) The force-deformation relationship between ultimate drifts θ_u and θ_{u2} may be a linear softening branch (Figure 11.1) or a sudden drop down to the reduced shear force, followed by a constant branch. After θ_{u2} damage level, a residual shear force should be considered (eventually equal to zero in the case of brittle failure mechanisms). A simplified bilinear force-deformation relationship until the θ_{u2} drift threshold is reached may be adopted, followed by a sudden drop down to zero of the shear force, in particular in the case of regular buildings with rigid diaphragms.

NOTE For piers, damage level at θ_{u2} does not correspond to the condition in which the gravity loads (axial force) can no longer be supported; for spandrels, damage level at θ_{u2} represents the condition of extensive damage, but usually the lintel has not fallen down yet.

Figure 11.1 Force-deformation relationship for masonry elements

11.4.1.2.2 Elements failing in flexure

(1) The ultimate displacement capacity of an unreinforced masonry pier controlled by flexure should be expressed in terms of drift, for which the chord rotation $\theta_{i(j)}$ at the end section where the flexural resistance corresponding to $\theta_{f,u} = 0,01(1 - \nu)$ is attained, where ν is the normalised axial load defined in 11.4.1.1.2(2). The chord rotation is defined by Formulas (11.23) and (11.24).

$$\theta_i = r_i + \frac{u_0 - u_i}{H_i} \quad (11.23)$$

$$\theta_j = r_j + \frac{u_j - u_0}{H_j} \quad (11.24)$$

where:

u_0 is the transversal displacement at the contraflexure point;

$r_{i(j)}$ is the rotation at the end section i(j);

$H_{i(j)}$ is the distance between the section i(j) and the contraflexure point ($H_i + H_j = H$, where H is the height of the pier).

(2) The ultimate displacement capacity of an unreinforced masonry spandrel controlled by flexure should be expressed in terms of drift for which the chord rotation $\theta_{i(j)}$ at the end section where the flexural resistance corresponding to $\theta_{f,u}$ is attained. $\theta_{f,u}$ is given in a) or b), as appropriate:

11.4.1.2 In-plane deformation capacities of masonry elements

(3) The deformation capacity $\theta_{f,u2}$ of masonry piers and spandrels controlled by flexure (see Figure 11.4a) should be expressed in terms of drift ratio and be taken equal to 4/3 of the values in (1) and (2) of this sub-clause, respectively ($\theta_{f,u2} = 4/3 \theta_{f,u}$).

(4) For piers, the reduced shear force corresponding to $\theta_{f,u2}$ is a portion of the shear resistance, which may depend on the type of masonry. This portion may be assumed to be 90% of the shear resistance for regular masonry and 80% for irregular masonry. This shear force is kept up as residual strength even after the deformation $\theta_{f,u2}$.

11.4.1.2.2 Elements failing in flexure

(1) The ultimate displacement capacity of an unreinforced masonry pier controlled by flexure should be expressed in terms of drift, for which the chord rotation $\theta_{i(j)}$ at the end section where the flexural resistance corresponding to $\theta_{fv} = 0,01(1 - \nu)$ is attained, where ν is the normalised axial load defined in 11.4.1.1.2(2). The chord rotation is defined by Formulas (11.23) and (11.24).

$$\theta_i = r_i + \frac{u_0 - u_i}{H_i} \quad (11.23)$$

$$\theta_j = r_j + \frac{u_j - u_0}{H_j} \quad (11.24)$$

where:

u_0 is the transversal displacement at the contraflexure point;

$r_{i(j)}$ is the rotation at the end section $i(j)$;

$H_{i(j)}$ is the distance between the section $i(j)$ and the contraflexure point ($H_i + H_j = H$, where H is the height of the pier).

11.4.1.2.3 Elements failing due to shear sliding

(1) The ultimate deformation capacity of an unreinforced masonry pier controlled by shear sliding should be expressed in terms of the chord rotation at the end section where the mechanism occurs and is taken equal to $\theta_{s,u} = 0,008$, unless the shear strength of the panel due to the failure of masonry units $V_{s,units}$ is attained (see Formula (11.19)), in which case $\theta_{s,u} = 0,006$.

(2) The deformation capacity $\theta_{s,u2}$ of an unreinforced masonry pier controlled by shear sliding (see Figure 11.5) should be expressed in terms of drift ratio and taken as 4/3 of the values in (1) of this sub-clause ($\theta_{s,u2} = 4/3 \theta_{s,u}$).

11.4.1.2.4 Elements failing due to diagonal cracking

(4) The ultimate displacement capacity of an unreinforced masonry pier controlled by diagonal cracking should be expressed in terms of drift ratio, by considering a representative measure for the entire panel defined as the average chord rotation of the two end sections, which may be approximated by the drift ratio defined in Formula (11.13). The limit threshold is $\theta_{d,u} = 0,006$ for regular (stair-stepped joints) and $\theta_{d,u} = 0,005$ for irregular masonry; in the case of modern masonry (hollow units) the limit threshold should be limited to $\theta_{d,u} = 0,0035$.

(5) The ultimate displacement capacity of an unreinforced masonry spandrel controlled by diagonal cracking is the same as for piers, given in (1) of this sub-clause.

(6) The deformation capacity $\theta_{d,u2}$ of unreinforced masonry piers and spandrels controlled by diagonal cracking (Figure 11.6a) should be expressed in terms of drift ratio and taken as 4/3 of the values in (1) and (2) respectively ($\theta_{d,u2} = 4/3 \theta_{d,u}$).

(7) The reduced shear force corresponding to $\theta_{d,u2}$ in a pier is a portion of the shear resistance. The recommended value is 50% of the shear resistance for regular masonry and 30% for irregular masonry. After $\theta_{d,u2}$ the pier is still able to support vertical gravity loads with a residual shear force of 20% of the shear resistance, for regular masonry, and without residual shear force, for irregular masonry.